

Hypocalcaemia Assessment: An Efficient Measure for Prevention of Seizures

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to assess and compare the levels of calcium in cases and controls with and without seizure disorders respectively. It also aimed to assess association of serum calcium levels with time since seizures and causes of seizures. This case control study conducted in Department of Medicine, People's Hospital Bhopal for a period of 18 months included 77 cases with seizure disorders and equal number of controls without seizure disorders. Data regarding detailed history regarding presenting complaints, time since onset of seizures, causes of seizures was obtained from cases. Mean calcium level amongst cases was 8.99 ± 0.75 mg/dl and that amongst controls was 9.32 ± 1.11 mg/dl. The present study observed significantly lower calcium level amongst cases as compared to controls ($p < 0.05$). No statistically significant association of mean calcium level was observed with time since seizures and various causes of seizures ($p > 0.05$). Serum calcium levels has significant association with seizures since there is some level of hypocalcemia in few though not all seizure patients. Calcium supplementation may be considered in patients with intractable seizures and in patients with drug refractory seizures. Thus calcium levels must be evaluated in every seizure patient irrespective of cause.

KEY WORDS: hypocalcemia, seizure, serum calcium

INTRODUCTION:

The word seizure is derived from a Latin word *sacire* meaning 'to take possession of'. Seizure is a convulsive incident due to aberrant, excessive, hypersynchronous emissions from an aggregate of CNS neurons.^[1] The incidence rate of seizures varies from 38 to 49.3 per 1 lakh population per year in India.^[2] When burst of electrical impulses in brain exceed the normal limits, it leads to seizure. Once generated, these impulses then spread to the adjacent neurons and results in uncontrolled electrical activity in brain. These may manifest as tonic clonic seizures characterized by uncontrolled jerking movements or may present as absent seizures i.e. momentary loss of awareness.^[3] Neuronal excitability is controlled by the balance between excitatory an inhibitory effects, both intrinsic and synaptic.^[4]

The etiology of seizures vary with age, e.g. trauma, cerebrovascular accidents, brain tumors and

metabolic causes are common cause of seizures in older age groups.^[5] Hypocalcemia-induced seizures are also one of the common cause of seizures. These seizures usually occur in patients with preexisting endocrinological abnormalities associated with poor calcium homeostasis.^[6] The role of calcium in seizure disorders could be attributed to reduced excitatory threshold, increased neural transmission, and increased neuromuscular excitation due to hypocalcemia.^[6] Also hypocalcemia can also be responsible for raised intracranial pressure, impaired cerebral functions and high susceptibility of neurons of hippocampus for epilepsy.^[7] The present study aimed to assess and compare the levels of calcium in cases and controls with and without seizure disorders respectively. It also aimed to assess association of serum calcium levels with time since seizures and causes of seizures.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The present case control study was conducted in Department of Medicine, People's Hospital Bhopal during 1st December 2017 to 30th May 2019. The study included 77 cases with seizure disorders and equal number of controls without seizure disorders. Ethical clearance was obtained from institute's ethical committee. All the participants were explained the

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Table 1: Distribution of socio-demographic variables among cases and controls.

Sociodemographic variables		Cases (n=77)		Controls (n= 77)		p value
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
Age group	≤20	10	13.0	6	7.8	0.29
	21-30	8	10.4	7	9.1	
	31-40	9	11.7	19	24.7	
	41-50	15	17.5	18	23.4	
	51-60	14	18.2	9	11.7	
	>60	21	27.3	18	23.4	
Gender	Male	46	59.7	57	74.0	0.06
	Female	31	40.3	20	26.0	

nature and purpose of study, and they were ensured that confidentiality would be maintained. The inclusion criteria for cases comprised of (a) patients diagnosed as having seizures admitted in People's Hospital and, (b) age group of 15 to 70 years of either gender. Those excluded were (a) patients not giving consent to participate in the study, (b) patients presenting after 72 hours from the onset of seizure, (c) pregnant and lactating females and/or (d) taking oral/parenteral magnesium and calcium. Similarly the inclusion criteria for participants of control group comprised of age and gender matched individuals without history of any seizure disorders in the age range of 15 to 70 years. However, individual not giving consent to participate in the study, pregnant/lactating females or taking oral/parenteral magnesium and calcium were excluded from the control group.

Those willing to participate and fulfilling the inclusion criteria of either group were enrolled during the study period. The option to withdraw from the study was always open. Details regarding sociodemographic variables was obtained from all the study participants of either group and entered in questionnaire. Data regarding detailed history regarding presenting complaints, time since onset of seizures, causes of seizures was obtained from cases. Blood sample was obtained from all the participants under aseptic precautions and subjected to RBS and Serum calcium estimation.

Data was compiled using MS excel and analyses using SPSS software version 20. Frequency was calculated for grouped data and expressed as percentage whereas numerical data was expressed as Mean and SD. Chi square test was used to assess the difference between quantitative variables whereas mean values between the groups were compared using independent t test. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to compare means between 3 variables. p value less than 0.05 was considered significant, whereas p value less than 0.01 was considered highly significant.

RESULTS:

The present study included 77 cases with mean age of 44.74 ± 16.73 years and 77 controls with mean age of 45.44 ± 15.52 years. Majority of cases in present study belonged to more than 60 years of age (27.3%), whereas majority of patients in control group belonged to 31 to 40 years of age. Maximum patients in both the groups were males i.e. 59.7% amongst cases and 74% amongst controls. However test of significance observed no statistical difference in age and gender composition between cases and control ($p > 0.05$) (Table 1).

Mean RBS in cases and controls was 129.64 ± 47.35 and 128.84 ± 31.79 mg/dl respectively in present study. Test of significance (unpaired t test) observed no statistical difference in mean RBS between cases and controls ($p > 0.05$). Mean calcium level amongst cases was 8.99 ± 0.75 mg/dl and that amongst controls was 9.32 ± 1.11 mg/dl. The present study observed significantly (unpaired t test) lower calcium level amongst cases as compared to controls ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 1).

In present study, mean calcium level within 24 hours of seizures was 8.94 ± 0.72 mg/dl whereas as mean calcium level between 24-48 hours and >48 hours was 9.15 ± 0.88 and 8.88 ± 0.64 mg/dl respectively. Test of significance (ANOVA) observed no statistically significant difference in mean calcium level amongst cases with time since seizures ($p > 0.05$). (Table 2) The present study observed no statistical difference in mean calcium level in various causes of seizures ($p > 0.05$) (Table 3).

DISCUSSIONS:

A seizure can be described as a paroxysmal event which can be due to abnormal, unnecessary, hypersynchronous discharges from an collection of CNS neurons.^[1] The present study assessed the serum calcium levels in case with seizure disorders and

Table 2: Association of time since seizure with calcium level amongst cases.

Calcium (mg/dl)	Time since seizure (Hours)		
	<24	24-48	>48
Mean	8.94	9.15	8.88
SD	0.72	0.88	0.64
p value	0.53		

Table 3: Association of cause of seizure with magnesium level amongst cases.

Calcium (mg/dl)	Cause		
	Organic	Metabolic	Unspecified
Mean	8.96	8.84	9.50
SD	0.73	0.69	0.93
p value	0.105		

compared them with healthy controls. Serum calcium levels are often associated with serious complications such as arrhythmias, seizures etc. Hypocalcemia has been defined as serum calcium level of <8.5mg/dl or ionized calcium level of <4 mg/dl.^[8] The normal serum calcium levels are maintained within very narrow range for optimal extracellular and intracellular functions.^[9] Normal level of serum calcium is maintained by multiple factors such as parathyroid hormone (PTH), calcitriol, vitamin D, serum magnesium serum phosphate level and ionized Ca itself.^[10] Thus alterations in Vitamin D, magnesium, PTH and calcitriol level may present with altered calcium levels.

Figure 1: Calcium level (mg/dl) among cases and controls.

The present study observed significantly (unpaired t test) lower calcium level amongst cases i.e. 8.99 ± 0.75 mg/dl as compared to controls i.e. 9.32 ± 1.11 mg/dl ($p < 0.05$). These findings are in concordance with the findings of Abdullahi I et al where mean serum calcium in the 60 cases was significantly lower than the control cases (2.3 ± 0.13 mmol/L vs. 2.4 ± 0.12 mmol/L; $p < 0.001$).^[11]

However, the reference study was conducted to assess the association of magnesium levels with seizure disorders and hypocalcemia might be secondary to magnesium imbalance. Victor et al in their study concluded that acute hypocalcemia is associated with increased neuromuscular excitability and tetany and thus the patients may present with seizures and altered mental status.^[12]

Calcium supplements in seizure disorders are known to inhibit small conducting Na^+ leak channel (NALCNs) and shifts dependency of voltage-gated sodium channels, reduces inward current through AMPA channels, and depresses the release of excitatory neurotransmitters and thus are helpful in reduction of seizure activity. This might explain the possibility of hypocalcemia in cases of seizures.^[13]

To our knowledge none of study have assessed the association of calcium levels with time since onset of seizures and etiologies. However the present study observed no statistically significant association of serum calcium levels with time since seizures as well as various causes.

CONCLUSION:

Serum calcium level has significant association with seizures since there is some level of hypocalcemia in few though not in all seizure patients. Calcium supplementation may be considered in patients with intractable seizures and in patients with drug refractory seizures. Thus calcium levels must be evaluated in every seizure patient irrespective of cause since it may help in preventing seizures.

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